

Derivation of the Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation (Sum of Kinetic Energy and Rest mass Energy) using Classical Mechanics

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Abstract: The Einstein's mass-energy equation is equal to the sum of rest mass energy and kinetic energy. This paper proves the sum of rest mass and kinetic energies which is equal to the Einstein's mass-energy equivalence.

Keywords: potential energy, rest mass energy, relativity

The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation

In classical mechanics, the total energy is equal to the sum of kinetic energy and potential energy. Here, the potential energy is considered as rest mass energy noted in the special theory of relativity [1-16]. Now, let us calculate the total energy of an object with non-zero mass (m) and velocity (v), where the velocity (v) is less than the speed of the light with zero mass.

Total Energy (E) = Kinetic Energy (K) + Potential Energy (P), i.e. $E = K + P$,

where $K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $P = mgh$.

Here, g denotes the gravitational acceleration of any object in the cosmos (space or universe) [18,19].

Now, let us prove that the potential energy or rest mass energy is equal to the kinetic energy. Suppose an object with the non-zero mass (m) and the velocity (v) falls freely from a height (s) due to gravity.

Then, the potential energy(P) = mgs . (1)

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = 0 + \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}gt^2. \quad (2)$$

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2gs \Rightarrow v^2 = 0 + 2gs \Rightarrow v^2 = 2g\left(\frac{1}{2}gt^2\right) \Rightarrow v^2 = g^2t^2. \quad (3)$$

By substituting the equation (2) in the equation (1), we get

$$P = mg \times s \Rightarrow P = mg \times \frac{1}{2}gt^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2. \quad (4)$$

By substituting the equation (3) in the equation (4), we conclude that

$$P = \frac{1}{2}mg^2t^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K. \quad (5)$$

Thus, it is proved that the potential energy is equal to the kinetic energy of the object.

$$\text{Therefore, total energy } (E) = K + P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = 2\left(\frac{1}{2}mv^2\right) = mv^2. \quad (6)$$

In the previous papers [16, 17] of the author of this article, the total energy (mv^2) has been proved using the following general equations of motion.

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}at^2 \text{ and } v^2 = u^2 + 2gs.$$

If we consider that the velocity (v) of the object mentioned above is equal to the speed of light (c), then $E = mc^2$. But, the velocity (v) of any object with non-zero mass is less than the speed of light.

Therefore, $E = mc_v^2$, where $c_v < c$.

If there is a value c_u such that $c_u < c$, then $c_u \leq c_v < c$.

Hence, $E \neq mc^2$.

In addition, the following references [1-17] give more information regarding the energy of an object in motion.

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